

Preparation of Nanophotonics LiNbO₃ Thin Films and Studying Their Morphological and Structural Properties by Sol-Gel Method for Waveguide Applications

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Abstract—Lithium niobate (LiNbO₃) nanostructures are prepared on quartz substrate by the sol-gel method. They have been deposited with different molarity concentration and annealed at 500°C. These samples are characterized and analyzed by X-ray diffraction (XRD), Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) and Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM). The measured results showed an importance increasing in molarity concentrations that indicate the structure starts to become crystal, regular, homogeneous, well crystal distributed, which made it more suitable for optical waveguide application.

Keywords—Lithium niobate, morphological properties, Pechini method, thin film.

I. INTRODUCTION

LITHIUM NIOBATE (LiNbO₃) is presented as an important ferroelectric material. Its excellent piezoelectric, electro-optical, pyroelectric, and photo-refractive, properties made it very attractive material for integrated optics and photonic applications [1]-[5]. It is also employed in nonlinear optics for frequency conversion and in telecommunication for electro-optic modulation [6]-[10]. Recently for optical devices, due to their mechanical robustness, good availability, optical homogeneity, this crystal plays an important role as a high quality source material with low optical loss [11]-[14]. Thin films of nanophotonic LiNbO₃ have been studied for use in an integrated form with unique pyroelectric, piezoelectric, and nonlinear optical properties, which would make it an ideal material for the fabrication of surface acoustic wave (SAW) [15], optoelectronic, and optical devices [16].

LiNbO₃ thin films were prepared using various experimental techniques such as sputtering [17], [18], sol-gel [19], [20], liquid phase epitaxial (LPE) [21], metal organic chemical vapor deposition (MOCVD) [22]-[24], soft-

chemistry [25], hydrothermal methods [26], and pulsed laser deposition (PLD) [27], [28].

This paper reports on the production of LiNbO₃ nano and micro photonic crystal by utilizing the Pechini route (Sol-gel). The phase evolution with the molarities concentration was also studied by using XRD, SEM and AFM because it is the important part of our work and application on Optical waveguides from thin film nanoparticles LiNbO₃ nano- and micro-photonics.

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The preparation procedure of LiNbO₃ nanostructures is Nb₂O₅ (ultra-purity, 99.99%) and oxalic acid (A.P.) are used without further purification. The solution is prepared by mixing Li₂CO₃, Nb₂O₅, citric acid, and ethylene glycol. The molar ratio between Li₂CO₃ and Nb₂O₅ was 1:1 in order to maximize the formation of LiNbO₃ stoichiometry phase. Firstly, the LiCO₃, Nb₂O₅, and citric acid were dissolved in Ethylene Glycol with heating and stirring at 90°C for 8 hours, then mixed all together with continued heating and stirring at 90°C for 8 hours. To obtain homogeneous and crack-free films of LiNbO₃, the precursor was deposited by spin coating technique on quartz substrates at a spinning speed of 3000 rpm for 30 sec. Seven layers were prepared, the film was dried at 120°C for 10 min and was annealing (calcined) at 500°C for 2 hours in static air and oxygen atmosphere to remove the organics. The structural evolution of the as-prepared nanophotonics was examined using high-resolution X-ray diffraction (HR-XRD), (X'Pert Pro MRD PW3040 system diffractometer, PANalytical Company, Netherlands) equipped with Cu-K α -radiation of wavelength $\lambda = 0.15418$ nm at 40 kV and 30 mA. The scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (JOEL JSM-6460LV, Oxford instruments, Analytical Ltd., Japan) was used to investigate the surface morphology of LiNbO₃, and atomic force microscopy (AFM) (SPM-9600, Scanning Probe Microscope, Shimadzu, Japan) was utilized for investigating the roughness of LiNbO₃. The thickness of the annealed samples was studied using scanning optical Reflectometer model (Filmetrics F20, China).

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III. RESULT AND DISSECTION

A. Structural Properties

The crystalline structure of LiNbO_3 nanophotonics was found to have hexagonal structure. It is observed from Fig. 1 that the peaks at $2\theta = 23.634, 32.637, 34.674, 48.355, 53.106,$ and 55.879 corresponding to (012), (104), (110), (024), (116) and (122) planes. Therefore, the film structure will be more crystalline with increasing molarity concentration as shown in Fig. 2. The measured structural properties of LiNbO_3 nanophotonics were listed in Table I. Crystallite size (D) was calculated using Scherrer's formula (1) [29].

$$D = K \lambda / \beta \cos \theta \quad (1)$$

where K is a constant taken to be 0.94, λ is the wavelength of X-ray used ($\lambda = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$), β is the full width at half maximum of XRD pattern and θ is Bragg's angle, around 26.41° . In

addition, the dislocation density (δ) and strain (ϵ) of LiNbO_3 nanophotonics were determined using the following relations (2), (3) [29].

$$\delta = 1/D^2 \quad (2)$$

$$\epsilon = \beta / 4 \tan \theta \quad (3)$$

The interplanar distance (d) was calculated for all sets of LiNbO_3 nanophotonics using Bragg's formula (4) [30].

$$d = h \lambda / 2 \sin \theta \quad (4)$$

where (h) is a positive integer for hexagonal structure and (d) is an interplanar distance as given in Table I.

The lattice parameters a and c were calculated by (5) [30]

$$\frac{1}{d^2} = \frac{4}{3} \left(\frac{h^2 + hk + k^2}{a^2} \right) + \frac{l^2}{c^2} \quad (5)$$

Fig. 1 XRD patterns of LiNbO_3 nanophotonics with different molarity concentrations: (a) 0.25 Mol/L, (b) 0.5 Mol/L, (c) 0.75 Mol/L and (d) 1 Mol/L

Fig. 1 shows the XRD pattern obtained from LiNbO_3 nanophotonics deposited on quartz substrates. All the peaks indicate to the hexagonal structure with lattice parameters $a = b = 5.1566, c = 13.858$, which were very close to the reported data in [19]. The nanophotonics have polycrystalline structure annealed at 500°C for 2 h in static air, two phases of LiNbO_3 could be recognized, Δ and δ . Δ phase was found to be more preferred despite that it has (012) orientation. The XRD clearly indicates the presence of a small amount of secondary Li deficient phase (LiNb_3O_8) at all molarity concentrations.

This phase is originated from an interface reaction between the oxygen and LiNbO_3 , that could be detected by XRD due to its high crystallization temperature at peaks $2\theta = 24.407, 30.262$ and 35.981 correspond to (400), (410) and (212) planes. There were an impurity like Nb_2O_5 , where detected as shown at peaks $2\theta = 24.433$ and 31.623 correspond to (-105) and (014) planes.

The measured lattice constants had showed good agreement with experimental values as given in Table I.

TABLE I
THE LiNbO₃ NANOPHOTONICS PARAMETERS AT 3000 RPM COATING SPEED AND ANNEALED AT 500 °C FOR 2 HOURS USING XRD DATA

Concentration Mol/L	Orientation hkl	Peak (θ)	Particle size (nm)	Dislocation density (δ) (10^9) (lines/m ²)	Strain (10^{-3})	d_{hkl} (Å)	Lattice constants a and c (Å)	Roughness (nm)
0.25	012	23.634	128.195	6.085	1.764	3.76152	a=5.1566, c=13.85	10.6
	104	32.637	116.644	7.350	1.681	2.740457	a=5.1566, c=13.85	
	110	34.674	102.744	9.473	1.182	2.583967	a=5.1566, c=13.85	
	024	48.355	107.506	8.653	0.836	1.880044	a=5.1566, c=13.85	
	116	53.106	97.410	10.539	2.954	1.722497	a=5.1566, c=13.85	
0.50	122	55.879	82.754	14.602	2.783	1.6434	a=5.1566, c=13.85	12.9
	012	23.709	100.213	9.957	1.758	3.748	a=5.1566, c=13.85	
	104	32.701	111.105	8.292	2.516	2.735	a=5.1566, c=13.85	
	110	34.824	93.393	11.465	2.353	2.573	a=5.1566, c=13.85	
	024	48.516	98.680	10.269	1.092	1.874	a=5.1566, c=13.85	
0.75	116	53.230	83.507	13.340	3.436	1.719	a=5.1566, c=13.85	15.4
	122	56.123	75.570	17.511	1.384	1.637	a=5.1566, c=13.85	
	012	23.709	87.213	13.147	1.757	3.748	a=5.1566, c=13.85	
	104	32.701	102.210	9.572	1.258	2.735	a=5.1566, c=13.85	
	110	34.824	79.089	15.987	1.569	2.573	a=5.1566, c=13.85	
1	024	48.516	84.544	13.991	1.365	1.874	a=5.1566, c=13.85	16.0
	116	53.230	80.970	15.253	0.736	1.719	a=5.1566, c=13.85	
	122	56.123	72.678	18.932	1.846	1.637	a=5.1566, c=13.85	
	012	23.709	84.213	14.101	1.757	3.748	a=5.1566, c=13.85 5.49340 [31] 13.8669 [31]	
	104	32.701	98.658	10.274	1.677	2.735	a=5.1566, c=13.85	
1	110	34.824	77.279	16.745	1.177	2.573	a=5.1566, c=13.85	16.0
	024	48.516	81.544	15.039	1.365	1.874	a=5.1566, c=13.85	
	116	53.230	78.581	16.194	1.375	1.719	a=5.1566, c=13.85	
1	122	56.123	70.678	20.018	1.846	1.637	a=5.1566, c=13.85	

B. Morphological Properties

1. SEM

It is a very interesting parameter for integrated-optic and optoelectronic applications. Fig. 2 shows SEM images (5*5 μ m) of LiNbO₃ nanostructures deposited on quartz substrates at different molarity concentrations. Since the density of nucleation for the LiNbO₃ thin films was not uniformly distributed on the flat substrate with different molarity concentration. At least molarity concentrations note that the

emergence of a high proportion of the pores and voids, these pores as a result of these impurities impact like Nb₂O₅, the LiNbO₃ thin films grew smoothly at higher molarity concentration that leads to perfect distribution better than the lower molar concentration Fig. 1. On the other hand, the structure is more homogenous at higher molar concentration. As discussed earlier, this suggests that higher molarity concentration leads to increase in regular distribution of LiNbO₃ nano and micro structures

Fig. 2 Surface morphology of LiNbO_3 nanostructures at different molarity concentrations. (a) 0.25 Mol/L, (b) 0.5 Mol/L, (c) 0.75 Mol/L and (d) 1 Mol/L

2. AFM

The grain size and root mean square could be affected by molarity concentration. Fig. 3 shows AFM images of the LiNbO_3 nanostructures with uniform dense surface and exhibits a decrease in grain size as the molarity concentration increases. The surface topography of LiNbO_3 nanostructures as observed from the AFM micrographs proves that the grains are uniformly distributed within the scanning area ($5 \mu\text{m} \times 5 \mu\text{m}$), with individual columnar grains extending upwards. This surface characteristic is quoted from the topographic images that found at 1.00 Mol to be uniform, smooth, and more homogeneous than others. In association with the increase of the average diameter of grain size from 84 to 128 nm, large grains appear on the proportion of solvent Fig. 3 (a). On the other hand, we note that the surface roughness increases as the molarity concentration increase because of the lack of solubility and inversely correlation with grain size. So, the roughness is ranging between 10.6 – 16.0 nm. Also, the average surface roughness was sufficiently leveled to prepare the devices.

The thickness was determined using an optical reflectometer. In the same time, the thickness increases as the

molarity concentration increase, which leads to increase the deposition process and number of atoms as shown in Fig. 4, the increasing molarity affects negatively on the grain size that guides to smoothen the surface.

IV. CONCLUSION

The LiNbO_3 nanostructures have been chemically prepared by spin-coating technique. Based on XRD results, the LiNbO_3 nanophotonics have polycrystalline in nature. The highest intensity shown at orientation (012) at $2\theta = 23.634$, a significant increasing as the spin coating speed at 3000 rpm. As expected, the structure is more crystalline as the molarity concentration increases. Also, SEM explains the nanostructures will be more homogenous as the molarity concentration increases. Morphology gives homogeneity, topography shows grain size decreasing from 128 to 84 nm and roughness is ranging between 10.6 – 16.0 nm as molarity increase due to the lack of solubility and inversely correlated with grain size. The result explained that the highest value of molarity concentrations are more appropriate for optical waveguide.

Fig. 3 AFM images of LiNbO₃ nanostructures at different molarity concentrations. (a) 0.25 Mol/L, (b) 0.5 Mol/L, (c) 0.75 Mol/L and (d) 1 Mol/L

Fig. 4 Thickness of LiNbO₃ nanostructures at at different molarity concentrations and at room temperature

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